

Blue straggler stars in galactic open clusters

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The so-called Blue Straggler Stars (BSS) are exotic objects present in all stellar environments, whose nature and formation channels are still partially unclear. In the colour-magnitude (CMD) diagram of a stellar system, they appear blueward and above the turnoff (TO), on the continuation of the main sequence. This position is incompatible with the predictions of the standard stellar evolution theory of single stars, and multiple mechanisms have been proposed for their formation. In particular, in stellar clusters, BSS could be the product of direct collisions or mergers in dynamical encounters, the merger of a contact binary, mass transfer activity in binary systems, or the merger of an inner binary in a hierarchical triple system via Kozai-Lidov mechanisms. Hence, this population is extremely important because it can provide information on the dynamics, the binary population, and the history of the stellar evolution of the system they belong to. An extensive review of the BSS properties has recently been presented in [1].

BSS seem to find themselves particularly comfortable in open clusters (OCs). These systems hold many lessons about the origins of the BSS. Given their sparse nature and proximity, they enable an in-depth analysis of basic BSS characteristics such as frequency, orbital parameters, and masses. In this context, large and homogeneous catalogues are needed to properly understand, identify, and characterize this population. By searching relations between the straggler population and the cluster properties (e.g., mass, age, binary fraction) we can identify potential clusters for further targeted multi-epoch radial-velocity monitoring, and so reveal their properties and provide evidence to support or rule out the formation mechanisms so far proposed. Drawbacks of previous catalogue of BSS in OCs [2, 3] are the lack of homogeneity of the open cluster data available at the time they were published, and the uncertain membership of the BSS candidates. Now, however, by taking advantage of the *Gaia* DR2 survey, we can determine accurate membership and, consequently, put the study of BSS in OCs on a much more solid statistical ground for the first time. This work presents a new catalogue of blue straggler stars in a large sample of OCs. It is based on the inspection of the CMDs of 408 clusters, and a membership characterisation provided by the *Gaia* DR2 astrometric solution.

Main results

In total, 897 blue straggler candidates were identified in the 408 OCs investigated. The number of clusters with at least one blue straggler is 111 (27.20%). In comparison with [2] and [3], our percentage is $\sim 30\%$ and $\sim 20\%$ lower, respectively. Figure 1 shows the combined colour-magnitude diagram for all our straggler candidates, corrected for distance and extinction, and coloured accord-

ing to the cluster age. We see that the brightest BSS are in the young clusters, as expected, and they become progressively fainter in older clusters. Some general highlights from our work are i) no blue straggler candidates were found in clusters with $\log(\text{age}) \leq 7.3$ (20 Myr) ii) the number of BSS in clusters with ages below 1 Gyr is relatively low, and around 70% (623) of them are in clusters older than $\log(\text{age}) = 9.3$ (2 Gyr) iii) there are on average 2.19 BSS per cluster.

Figure 1: Colour-magnitude diagram showing dereddened, corrected-by-distance BSS candidates. The BSS are coloured according to the cluster age.

When comparing our catalogue with [3], we found large inconsistencies; for individual clusters, the percentage of BSS found to be non-members according to our criteria is about 10–60% of that catalogue. However, it is possible to retrieve about 70–100% of the BSS of [3] in close and very well studied clusters, specially in those with spectroscopic studies, like, e.g., NGC 188.

Using 107 clusters and BSS with membership probability $P_{\text{memb}} \geq 80\%$, we explored the dependency of the ratio $N_{\text{BSS}}/N_{\text{MSS}}^{\text{ss}}$ and the cluster age (see Figure 2), metallicity, distance, and reddening. When comparing with the cluster age, we found two trends: i) $N_{\text{BSS}}/N_{\text{MSS}}$ is approximately constant—flat—for young clusters, until $\log(\text{age}) \sim 8.7$ (500 Myr, $M_{\text{TO}} = 2.4 M_{\odot}$), and ii) the ratio shows a steep increase with cluster age starting from $\log(\text{age}) = 9.0$ (1 Gyr, $M_{\text{TO}} = 1.81 M_{\odot}$) towards later ages. We also observed the plateau described by [4] in the range $9.3 < \log(\text{age}) < 9.6$. We can safely assume that the older clusters harbour more BSS. No clear relation with the cluster metallicity [Fe/H], distance, or reddening was found.

Although the anti-correlation between the specific frequency $N_{\text{BSS}}/N_{\text{HB}}$ and the integrated magnitude M_V

^{ss} N_{MSS} is the number of cluster main sequence stars down to 1 magnitude below the TO, adopted as a proxy of the cluster richness.

shown by [5] still holds for OCs using our data, this follows a different distribution, more similar to the one described by the globular clusters (GCs) in the same reference.

When comparing the total mass (M_{tot}) and the number of blue stragglers N_{BSS} ^{¶¶}, we found a power-law relation of the form $N_{\text{BSS}} \propto M_{\text{tot}}^{0.3-0.43(\pm 0.15)}$, very similar to the one found for GCs by [6] ($N_{\text{BSS}} \propto M_{\text{tot}}^{0.38 \pm 0.04}$). This could indicate that binaries dominated BSS formation in both type of clusters, and that the formation and evolution of BSS is quite similar in both open and globular clusters.

Figure 2: Ratio $N_{\text{BSS}}/N_{\text{MSS}}$ as a function of the age in logarithmic scale. Errors are Poisson statistics.

Additionally we analysed in detail the BSS population of four old clusters—Collinder 261, NGC 2477, Trumpler 5, and Trumpler 20. The clusters were observed with FLAMES@VLT and the data were collected between January 2012 and March 2018, under ESO-programs 88.D-0045(A) and 0100.D-0052(A). By using the radial velocity variability technique, we assessed the BSS membership and classified them into members, non-members, close binaries (CB), and long-period binaries (LP); for more details, see [7, 8]. The spectra obtained for radial velocities also allowed us to obtain measurements of the projected rotational velocities. In all we found 10 CB (all within $30 \text{ km/s} \leq v \sin i \leq 270 \text{ km/s}$),

1 LP ($v \sin i = 30 \text{ km/s}$), 7 member non-variable stars (all within $10 \text{ km/s} \leq v \sin i \leq 40 \text{ km/s}$), one non-variable yellow straggler ($v \sin i = 10 \text{ km/s}$), and 3 non-members. It is possible that these non-velocity-variable BSS are indeed long-period binaries, perhaps outside of our detection limit. For those stars with data in the literature (3 BSS in Collinder 261), we estimated their masses. To fit the orbits we used our radial velocities and the periods reported in the literature. To derive the values of the mass of the secondaries (M_2), we first estimated the masses of the primaries (M_1) from the CMD. Finally, we obtained a M_2 for Crd261-BS4, Crd261-BS5, and Crd261-BS8, of $0.118 \pm 0.005 M_{\odot}$, $0.21 \pm 0.01 M_{\odot}$, and $0.42 \pm 0.02 M_{\odot}$ respectively.

Finally, by cross-matching our catalogue with the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS), we found that 40% of BSS in Collinder 261 (9 Gyr) are in short-period binaries with orbital periods between 5 hours and 3 days. These results are at odds with the fraction of short-period binaries found among BSS in old open clusters (e.g., NGC 188 with 7 Gyr, and M67 with 4 Gyr), and may tell us important facts about the relative importance of the BSS formation mechanism as a function of the age of the cluster.

Conclusions

We have provided the scientific community with a new, internally consistent and homogeneous catalogue of BSS candidates in Galactic open clusters. We found 897 BSS in 408 OCs in the 1 Myr–10 Gyr age range. We have confirmed that the number of BSS increases with cluster age and cluster mass. Finally, we have performed the first spectroscopic analysis of the blue straggler population in four open clusters, where different types of binaries were identified among them.

References

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^{¶¶}This comparison was carried out using clusters with $N_{\text{BSS}} \geq 10$.